

Bringing values to standardisation: From policy concepts to a value-based framework for education about standardisation

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Abstract

The present paper investigates the relationship between the European Commission's policy vision for standardisation and current educational practices in European universities. The study is motivated by the following observation: although EU policy documents emphasise the need for a human-centric and responsible approach to standardisation, including the integration of ethical and societal considerations, recent research reveals that these aspects are largely absent in the teaching portfolios of recognised standardisation educators in European universities. More so, the educators find it difficult to understand how to assess or ensure that their teaching complies with the policy-invited orientation. This work examines the relevant EU policy documents to understand how the notion of responsible standardisation is framed and proposes a solution that emphasises the inclusion of specific values in standardisation education. This involves enlisting the rather abstract EU core values and interests and translating them into more tangible and familiar concepts for educators, such as competencies, knowledge, and skills, on the basis of a value-based Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) framework. Since ILOs are traditionally used for aligning educational programmes with labour market and policy demands, they offer a practical tool for this transformation. By identifying current knowledge gaps and proposing actionable solutions, this paper advances the discourse on responsible standardisation and lays the groundwork for implementing value-based education about standardisation, fostering the development of educational models that reflect novel societal needs, ethical values, and support the EU's political vision for value-based standardisation.